

PRESERVATION AND MUSEIFICATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE MUSEUM OF MATERIAL CULTURE AND ITS ARCHITECTURAL ENSEMBLE OF THE 19TH CENTURY

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the study of the processes of preservation and museification of immovable cultural heritage objects using the example of the Museum of Material Culture and its architectural ensemble of the 19th century in Tashkent. The article examines the evolution of the concept of museification in the context of the development of museology as a scientific discipline, as well as its interdisciplinary application in the field of monument protection, architecture and restoration. Based on a specific case, a set of practical measures for the preservation of the object is analyzed, including scientific research, restoration, conservation, adaptation to the museum function and ensuring public access. Special attention is paid to the long-term process of restoring the integrity of the building, overcoming legal and property obstacles, as well as countering the threats associated with urbanization, the construction boom and the loss of historical buildings. The article reveals systemic problems in the field of cultural heritage protection in Uzbekistan, including imperfect legislation, legal gaps in land ownership, administrative barriers and pressure from development interests. The unique experience of including a private facility in the state register of immovable cultural heritage and related institutional procedures is considered separately. It is concluded that effective museification requires not only a scientific and restoration approach, but also comprehensive legal regulation, interdepartmental interaction and an active position of the owner as a key actor in the preservation of cultural heritage.*

Keywords: *museification; cultural heritage; immovable monuments; architectural heritage of the 19th century; preservation of historical buildings; restoration; conservation; urbanization; gentrification; legal conflicts; land privatization; monument protection; museum institutionalization; historical and cultural value; Tashkent; urban development; state register of heritage; cultural policy.*

Having accumulated a professional vocabulary and a sufficient number of generalizing works, museology at the end of the 20th century received a boost in development and became an independent discipline. Up to this point, only movable historical objects were included in the field of activity, the inclusion of intangible and immovable heritage has become an integral part of science. The concept of "museification", which came into use back in the twenties of the last century, finally gained full significance as a process of turning monuments of cultural, natural and intangible heritage into museum objects for their preservation, study, demonstration and popularization. In addition to museology, today the term museification is used in the science of monument protection, the history of art and architecture, and restoration theory, considering monuments as objects that arose as a result of historical events and phenomena, allowing us to explore their context, stylistic nature, and aesthetic criteria.

The process of museification includes scientific research, restoration, conservation, the creation of a permanent exhibition and providing access to the public, which allows not only to save monuments from destruction, but also to include them in modern cultural life, to ensure maximum preservation of the value of the object, to identify its historical, cultural and scientific significance in order to create conditions for visitors to visit the object as a result the location of the museum institution in it. In addition to conservation and numerous steps of physical preservation of the object and its introduction into museum use, in the process of museification of the building at M. Gandhi 32 over the course of 35 years, tremendous work has been done in a number of areas, ranging from a ten-year process of gradual purchase and consolidation of parts of the building into a single possession, a long-term series of legal conflicts in the fight against gentrification and vandalism by officials, and finally a long-term scientific study and analysis of the history and cultural value of the object, the time and context of its appearance in this place has developed to the present day, including the composition of buildings and the determination of their age based on maps and archival data about existing buildings, as well as about the street, its inhabitants and the historical context of the formation of a new city, the history of Tashkent's development and the continuity of urban planning, since understanding the historical and artistic features of the monument turns it into an independent museum display object. In addition to extensive restoration work, a set of measures was carried out aimed at creating conditions for the placement of a cultural institution in the architectural monument and its functioning in a museum environment, while preserving the architectural forms and artistic features of the building, maximizing the authenticity of the monument while ensuring its accessibility for study and inspection.

Until 2000, the concentration of preserved architecture from the Russian Art Nouveau period, as well as characteristic of merchant Tashkent of this period, was highest in the Hamid Alimjan metro area, but with the onset of the construction boom due to an active renovation program, only individual buildings remained in scattered locations. The construction boom of the twenties of the second millennium almost completely destroyed Lakhtinskaya Street. Of all the buildings at the end of the 19th century, the building that was converted into the Kindergarten of the Consumers Union in the nineties was saved because it was bought by a commercial bank, but after reconstruction it appeared in a modified and almost unrecognizable form. The second existing building of this time, which is discussed in the dissertation, was not only preserved, but also returned by the efforts of the owner to the condition in which it was under construction. After the revolution, the houses were municipalized and transferred to the city housing stock, to which they remained until 1937, when, in the same settled and condensed form, they were transferred to various organizations and became departmental.

The house, which was divided room by room and turned into an apartment, was bought out for 9 years from 1990 to 1999 from fourteen families, each of whom, over the course of a hundred years, at the cost of systematically destroying the house, consistently built separate living conditions in it: additional walls were erected, original doorways were sealed and new ones were made, stoves were demolished, bathrooms and gas stoves were installed, destroying deck boards and antique floor tiles, etc. This was followed by the process of combining individual holdings under a single number and personal account. After the so-called common yard was completely bought out by one owner, it became possible to make a decision by the Khokim of the city to include the yard's land plot in the household plan, which was done, and

each of the procedures took up to six months and required iron perseverance and diligence in communicating with officials, which was by no means always productive.

For example, according to the norms of civil engineering, a building with a century and a half of history, built of adobe, has already exhausted itself twice, both physically and mentally, and exists without a price only thanks to investments and personal efforts of the owner to maintain the house in decent condition. However, in the registers of the tax inspectorate and the cadastre, the house is listed as a burnt brick building on a concrete base with an indeterminate age, and instead of depreciation over its service life, it is regularly overestimated by them, becoming many times more expensive over the years, which accordingly affects the fact that the property tax on this building is growing exponentially, and given the total area of one thousand square meters, this significant funds. Such appeals or attempts to clarify such paradoxical situations are usually useless.

In 2017, in the midst of restoration work on the house, a construction boom hit it, and in the interests of a group of businessmen who took over Telman Park, a decision was made to demolish a number of houses adjacent to it for unclear purposes, either to increase parking or to build a hotel. Long-term opposition to this illegal decision led to its cancellation, which became one of the few positive precedents for the preservation of cultural heritage. Unfortunately, further attempts to preserve the historical buildings of Lakhtinskaya Street were unsuccessful.

The wave of urbanization has led to massive violations of citizens' rights and their ability to protect themselves from the country's sweeping demolitions of private homes and evictions during the construction boom that began in 2017, also challenging the country's cultural heritage and historical buildings. The situation required international monitoring and the mission of the UN Special Rapporteur, which took place in Uzbekistan in 2024, but its conclusions and recommendations were not implemented, and the endless adoption of declarative new acts to streamline the situation created a precedent for complete disregard of the law and its final discrediting. In the absence of effective legal remedies and legal awareness, masquerading as a public need, predatory weaning and expropriation of the property of legitimate owners in favor of private construction contractors took place on the basis of documents obtained through forgery and corruption issued by local city authorities or without them at all, accompanied by intimidation of both citizens themselves and repression of human rights defenders, representatives of civil society and social networks where One of the largest groups in the Uzbek segment of Facebook, called - demolition, was deleted., It has been in existence since April 2017, and had about 32,000 subscribers. The absence of a General Architectural Plan, followed by endless arbitrary changes to it in the absence of a holistic vision for the further development of the city, excluding the participation of citizens and representatives of the expert community in urban planning processes, as a result, led to the destruction of the historical buildings and infrastructure of the city, green spaces were destroyed, the urban environment was disfigured and engineering communications were overloaded¹.

One of the reasons that made the above violations possible was a paradoxical property conflict or legal lacuna in the legislation on land ownership, as a result of which citizens were granted only the right to lifelong use of land plots with housing in their lifetime possession, that is, citizens owned the building, but not the land on which it was located. In 2022, according to

¹ Проблемы урбанизации, неэффективное законодательство и стихийные стройки. Спецдокладчик ООН доложил о результатах своей миссии в Узбекистане <https://podrobno.uz/cat/obchestvo/problemy-urbanizatsii-neeffectivnoe-zakonodatelstvo-i-stikhiynye-stroyki-spetsdokladchik-oon-dolozhi/>

Cabinet Resolution No. 71 of February 14, 2022, in accordance with the Law "On the Privatization of Non-agricultural Land", in the midst of the seizure of citizens' property, the procedure for the privatization of land plots was finally determined and adopted., owned by individuals and legal entities, and most importantly, on the third attempt, a scale for estimating the value of land based on zoning and adequate prices was approved, which slowed down the process, unlike previous iterations and attempts to ratify this law based on the fact that citizens were actually offered not the privatization of land for buildings they already owned, but its purchase from the state for commercial or market value. As soon as the privatization process was launched, it was immediately done by the owner of the House in order to further protect its cultural significance and value from further attempts to demolish it².

The house also became the first and only experience in Uzbekistan of adding a privately owned historical site to the National List of state-protected Immovable Objects of Tangible Cultural Heritage. According to the Resolution of the Council of Ministers "On approval of the Regulations on the State Register of Immovable Objects of Tangible Cultural Heritage" dated October 4, 2019³. The appeal of the owner of the object to the Agency of Cultural Heritage of the Republic of Uzbekistan, carried out in compliance with all the rules, took place on April 26, 2023, and on May 31, 2023, a positive decision and an extract from the Agency's protocol were made on it. Two years later, on May 12, 2025, according to the procedure, the Cabinet of Ministers notified through the press about the inclusion of 130 additional objects of tangible cultural heritage, including the residential building No. 32 on Mahatma Gandhi Street in the state register of objects of tangible cultural heritage of real estate⁴.

The full list of 130 sites proposed for inclusion in the list was also published, and its discussion in the Cabinet of Ministers was supposed to last until May 23, 2025, after which it would enter into force. However, the final entry into force of changes in the national list of tangible cultural heritage real estate was announced only a year later, taking more than three years, which presumably took numerous interdepartmental approvals and the allocation of a 200-meter conservation zone around the facility, in which demolition and other construction work are preventatively prohibited in order to preserve it.

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2. Постановление Кабинета Министров Республики Узбекистан, от 14.02.2022 г. № 71 <https://www.lex.uz/en/docs/5858017>
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² Постановление Кабинета Министров Республики Узбекистан, от 14.02.2022 г. № 71 <https://www.lex.uz/en/docs/5858017?ONDATE=14.02.2022>

³ Постановление Кабинета Министров Республики Узбекистан № 846 от 04.10.2019 Об утверждении национального перечня объектов недвижимости материального культурного наследия <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/4543266#>

⁴ В список объектов наследия планируется включить здание Кабмина, могилу Савицкого и дом №22 на ул. Ш. Руставели <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2025/05/12/cultural-heritage/>

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